

FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH RATE BEHAVIOUR OF 9310 STEEL UNDER CONSTANT- AND VARIABLE-AMPLITUDE LOADING

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Fatigue-crack-growth tests were conducted on compact specimens made of 9310 steel under constant-amplitude loading and single-spike overloads. Specimens were tested over a wide range in load ratios ($0.1 \leq R \leq 0.9$) to generate ΔK -rate data from threshold to near fracture. Several loading sequences were used to generate near threshold test data: compression pre-cracking constant amplitude (CPCA) or load reduction (CPLR), and ASTM E-647 load reduction (LR). Results were compared with test data from the literature using the same procedures on thinner C(T) specimens. Very little difference was observed between the various test methods. Some load-history effects were shown in the threshold regime for ASTM LR and CPLR tests. Test data correlated well in the near-threshold regime using FASTRAN, a life-prediction code, where a plane-strain constraint factor ($\alpha = 2.5$) was required. Under variable-amplitude loading, a constraint-loss (plane strain to plane stress) behaviour was required to match the test data.

INTRODUCTION

Fatigue-crack growth (FCG) has been a major contributor to structural failures due to repeated cyclic loads. Linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) has proven to be a powerful tool in understanding FCG and in the quantification of the cyclic stress-intensity-factor range (ΔK) with respect to FCG rate at a given load ratio ($R = \text{minimum to maximum load}$). The relation between ΔK and rate (dc/dN) was shown to be nearly linear on a log-log space (Paris and Erdogan [1]). However, the relationship between ΔK and dc/dN becomes non-linear once cracked bodies are approaching fracture [2] or when the FCG rate is very slow [3]. Therefore, fatigue-crack growth behaviour of many materials are categorised into three regions: (1) threshold region (ΔK is low and rates are extremely slow), (2) mid-region (crack-growth rate is roughly linear with the stress-intensity factor), and (3) fracture region (large crack-growth rates). Crack-closure behaviour, discovered by Elber [4], has been shown to be a major mechanism in explaining the effects of load ratio, low crack-growth rate behaviour in the near-threshold region, and retardation/acceleration due to an overload/underload, which modifies the stress-intensity-factor range experienced at the crack tip. Hence, crack-growth rates are affected by the contact of residual plastic deformations left in the wake of the moving crack [5], roughness of the fatigue-crack surfaces [6], and debris created along the crack surfaces [7]. Crack-growth data under constant-amplitude loading has been correlated using the crack-closure concept over a wide range in load levels, load ratios, and have covered a wide range in rates from threshold to fracture [8].

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ASTM E-647, standard on fatigue-crack growth [9], uses load-reduction procedures to generate constant load-ratio data in the threshold and near-threshold regions. However, the ASTM load-reduction method has been shown to produce higher thresholds (ΔK_{th} at $1.0E-10$ m/cycle) and slower rates in the near-threshold regime than steady-state constant-amplitude data for a large number of materials [10-12]. In the past, the load-reduction procedure has also been shown to produce fanning in the measured crack-growth rates with load ratio in the threshold regime. (Fanning in the near-threshold regime gives more spread in the ΔK -rate data compared to the mid-region.) The load-reduction test method has also been shown to induce higher crack-opening loads and remote crack-surface closure due to a load and/or environmental history effects [13-15]. Thus, a compression pre-cracking method [16-17] had been developed to generate constant-amplitude fatigue-crack-growth-rate data in the threshold and near-threshold regimes with minimal or no load-history effects. The procedure involves cycling a notched specimen under a compression-compression loading to initiate a crack at the crack-starter notch, and then testing the specimen under constant-amplitude loading. The initial crack is grown several compressive plastic-zone sizes, ρ_c , to eliminate the effects of the tensile residual stresses, the crack-starter notch effects, and to stabilise the crack-opening-load history [12]. This procedure is called the compression pre-cracking constant-amplitude (CPCA) loading test method. Another procedure is compression pre-cracking load-reduction (CPLR) testing. The latter method allows the crack to be grown at a much lower initial ΔK_i value than allowed in the current ASTM standard load-reduction test procedure (ΔK_i at $1.0E-8$ m/cycle), which requires tensile pre-cracking. However, the CPLR method has also been shown to induce some load-history effects depending upon the magnitude of the initial stress-intensity-factor range before starting load reduction.

Standard mechanical measurements have been employed to measure bulk effects, like crack-mouth-opening displacement (CMOD) or back-face strain (BFS) gauges. These remote methods have been very successful in monitoring crack growth. However, the remote methods have not been successful in measuring crack closure (or more correctly, the Elber crack-opening load). Yamada and Newman [18-19], using a local strain-gauge method, showed that there is crack-closure behaviour in the near-threshold region attributed to residual plastic deformations, crack-surface roughness and/or fretting-debris along the crack surfaces from tests conducted at low R and even very high R during the load-reduction procedures. The phenomenon is called “high-R” closure. In the threshold and near-threshold regions, debris-induced crack closure (DICC) [7, 20] and roughness-induced crack closure (RICC) [6, 21] contributed to overall crack closure; but plasticity-induced crack closure (PICC) was still very relevant under all load-ratio conditions and contributed strongly to crack-opening loads that were above the minimum load [8, 12, 15].

Herein, a test programme was conducted to generate fatigue-crack-growth-rate data on 9310 steel ($B = 10.2$ mm) from threshold to near fracture using several loading sequences: (1) compression pre-cracking constant amplitude (CPCA), (2) compression pre-cracking load reduction (CPLR), and (3) ASTM load reduction (LR). Compact specimens were tested at load ratios (R) of 0.1, 0.4, 0.7 and 0.9. Comparison of stress-intensity-factor range against rate for the various load ratios were made with previous literature test data generated by Newman et al. [22] on a thinner 9310 steel ($B = 6.35$ mm). The Two-Parameter Fracture Criterion [23, 24] was used to characterise the fracture behaviour of compact specimens. A crack-closure analysis was made to develop an effective stress-intensity-factor range (ΔK_{eff}) against rate (dc/dN) relation from threshold to near fracture.

MATERIAL AND SPECIMEN CONFIGURATION

C(T) specimens, Figure 1(a), were machined from a 9310 steel rod with cracks perpendicular to the rolling direction and these specimens were obtained from the NASA Langley Research Center. The back-face strain (BFS) gauge method was used to monitor crack lengths and to measure crack-opening loads from remote load-strain records during the various tests.

Tensile properties were not obtained on this particular material. But, the yield stress (980 MPa) and ultimate tensile strength (1,250 MPa) were determined from seven (7) tensile specimens machined from a similar rod (see Ref. 22) in the current study. The tensile properties are important in the fracture toughness assessment of the steel. Compact specimens had a width, $w = 50.8$ mm, and a thickness, $B = 10.2$ mm. The edges of the pin holes in these specimens were not bevelled because the material was too hard and the BFS gauges were already installed on the specimens. However, the pin holes in C(T) specimens from the other test programme [22] were bevelled.

Bevelled or counter-bored pin holes in C(T) specimens, Figure 1(b), have been found to be useful in maintaining straight-crack fronts, as shown in Figure 2, during threshold (load-reduction) testing. The offset counter-bored or bevelled holes are being used to maintain the full thickness when compression loads are applied to the pin holes during pre-cracking to reduce the bearing stresses and to help prevent pin-hole cracking.

(a) Compact

(b) Offset counter-bored or bevelled pin holes

FIGURE 1 Compact test specimen and counter-bored or bevelled pin holes.

FIGURE 2 Crack-front shape near threshold in 4340 steel compact specimens [22, 25].

TEST PROCEDURES FOR COMPRESSION PRE-CRACKING

There are three procedures available for generating low crack-growth rate (near-threshold and threshold) test data: (1) compression pre-cracking constant-amplitude (CPCA), (2) compression pre-cracking load-increasing (CPLI), and (3) compression pre-cracking load-reduction (CPLR) testing. The loading sequences are shown in Figure 3.

The pre-cracking loads were applied as constant-amplitude loading with both the minimum and maximum load less than zero for C(T) specimens (i.e. compression-compression fatigue loading). The minimum compressive stress-intensity factor, K_{cp} , was

$$|K_{cp}| / E = 0.00018 \sqrt{m} \quad (0.0012 \sqrt{\text{in.}}) \tag{1}$$

where K_{cp} is the stress-intensity factor at the minimum applied load (i.e. largest compressive load), and E is the modulus of elasticity. A load ratio, R , of 10 to 20 were used, which gives a maximum compressive load that is 5 to 10% of the minimum load.

In the CPCA/CPLI procedures, compression fatigue loading is used to pre-crack the specimen. Then either constant-amplitude loading or load-increasing is used to grow the crack a specified distance ($\sim 2\rho_c$) to eliminate the effects created by the tensile residual stresses. Finally, constant amplitude loading or load increasing is used to generate near-threshold fatigue-crack-growth-rate test data for monotonically increasing stress-intensity factor.

In the CPLR procedure, compression loading is used to pre-crack the specimen, then constant amplitude loading or load increasing is used to grow the crack a specified distance ($\sim 2\rho_c$) through the tensile residual stress field. Finally, the K -decreasing constant- R test procedure (like that used in ASTM E-647 [9]) is used to generate near-threshold and threshold data. Note that the CPLR test may still generate load-history effects in the threshold regime depending upon the magnitude of the initial ΔK_i used before starting load reduction. Once threshold conditions are reached, continuation of the test at constant-amplitude or load-increasing procedures are recommended at a higher R value than that used during load reduction to avoid load-history effects. The test continuation should avoid crack closure of the crack surfaces created during the load-reduction test.

(a) CPCA/CPLI loading sequence

(b) CPLR loading sequence

FIGURE 3 Loading sequence for CPCA/CPLI and CPLR testing.

Figure 4 shows the results of a boundary-element analyses of standard C(T) specimens with a crack emanating from either a V-notch or U-notch with a notch-root radius of 0.1 or 0.2 mm, respectively. Analyses were conducted with the FADD2D code [26]. Crack extension from the notch is denoted as Δc . The stress-intensity factor for a crack emanating from the notch, K_{NCT} , is normalised by the standard K solution for the C(T) specimen [9]. For the V-notch, calculations have been made for either a 45- or 60-degree notch for a 76 mm-wide specimen with a notch length-to-width (c_n/w) ratio of 0.3. The notch height, h , was 2.54 mm ($w/h = 30$). For crack extension greater than $0.5h$ from the V-notch tip, the stress-intensity factors were within 1 percent of the standard K solution for C(T) specimens. For the U-notch, the EDM notch height was 0.4 mm with a width of 50 mm ($w/h = 125$). Here the crack extension has to be $0.75h$ to give stress-intensity factors within 1 percent of the standard K solution. Stress-intensity factors approach the standard K solution for crack lengths greater than $0.75h$. Although these results are for $c/w = 0.3$, it is expected that the ratios of K_{NCT}/K_{CT} would have similar behaviour for larger c/w ratios. However, the intent is to not account for the effects of the notch on stress-intensity factors, but to grow the crack beyond the influence of the notch.

FIGURE 4 Influence of crack-starter notch on stress-intensity factors.

FATIGUE-CRACK-GROWTH RATES AND FRACTURE ANALYSIS

Figure 5 shows a comparison of ΔK against rate for the various R values used in the test programme with test data from Ref. 22 using the same test procedures, but for a thinner 9310 material. All tests were conducted in laboratory air, at room temperature and, generally, at 18 Hertz. The FTA Crack Monitoring System [28] and the BFS gauge were used to monitor crack growth. The standard stress-intensity factor solution for the C(T) specimen [9] was used to calculate ΔK and the rates (dc/dN) were calculated using the point-to-point method.

The test data at $R = 0.9$ and 0.95 are shown in Figure 5(a). These data are important because the cracks are fully open and ΔK is essentially ΔK_{eff} in the threshold and near-threshold regimes. After compression pre-cracking, the load reduction procedure began at a rate of $\sim 2e-9$ m/cycle. Once the load-reduction test was terminated, constant-amplitude (CA) loading was then applied to grow the cracked specimen to failure. The test frequency was manually reduced to about 5 to 10 Hertz during the latter phase. Testing at $R = 0.95$ produced a slightly lower threshold than the test at $R = 0.9$. Vertical dashed line at $\Delta K = 2.5 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ is the estimated effective threshold based on a correlation of thresholds for aluminum alloys, titanium alloys and steels using the modulus of elasticity [27]. Cracks in the higher R test specimens grow to failure at lower ΔK values because fracture is controlled by K_{max} , since $\Delta K_c = K_c (1 - R)$, where K_c is the fracture toughness. (Note that the elastic fracture toughness is a function of crack length and width.)

Figures 5(b) and 5(c) show that the ΔK -rate data for $R = 0.7$ and 0.4 loading, respectively, are in remarkable agreement between the two thicknesses and two different 9310 rods. Note that the CPLR test at $R = 0.7$ is essentially the same as the ASTM LR method, except tensile pre-cracking loads are used to generate the pre-crack instead of compression. But at high R , like $R = 0.7$, very little difference has been observed between the two pre-cracking methods. The constant-amplitude test at $R = 0.4$ was preceded by a CPLR test at $R = 0.1$ to avoid load-history effects (residual plastic deformations created during the $R = 0.1$ test). Thus, the $R = 0.1$ CPLR test would not affect the $R = 0.4$ test at CA loading.

A comparison of the ΔK -rate data at $R = 0.1$ loading is shown in Figure 5(d). Again, there was remarkable agreement between the two thicknesses, except for one test. Initially, all of the thicker specimens were compression pre-cracked and then stored for testing. After a week or so, the first specimen was tested at an initial ΔK of about $8 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ under CA loading, but the test data (open red circles) did not appear to be correct based on previous testing. Thus, a second specimen was subjected to compression pre-cracking and immediately tested under CA loading. Here the test data agreed well with the previous test data on the thinner material. Therefore, the tensile residual stresses in the first test specimen may have relaxed over time and was not effective in growing the pre-crack. But residual stress measurements were not made. Hence, the CPCA or CPLR testing should be initiated immediately after compression pre-cracking to avoid potential residual-stress relaxation.

To evaluate the fracture toughness of the material, only the fatigue-crack-growth tests were available. In most tests, the cracks in the C(T) specimens were grown to failure under cyclic loading. Here, the final recorded crack length and the maximum fatigue load were used to calculate K_{Ie} (elastic stress-intensity factor at failure) and these results are shown in Figure 6 as solid circular symbols. The thicker material ($B = 10.2 \text{ mm}$) gave slightly lower fracture toughness values than the thinner material [22]. Most tests failed at large c_i/w ratios (> 0.7). For comparison, similar test results on a 4340 steel [25] are shown as square symbols. Here one specimen was fatigue cracked to a lower crack-length-to-width ratio and statically pulled to failure (solid square symbol).

A fracture criterion was derived [23, 24] that accounts for the elastic-plastic behaviour of a cracked material based on notch-strength analysis. The criterion is

$$K_F = K_{\text{Ie}} / \Phi \tag{2}$$

$$\Phi = 1 - m S_n / S_u \quad \text{for } S_n \leq \sigma_{\text{ys}} \tag{3}$$

$$\Phi = (\sigma_{ys}/S_n) (1 - m S_n/S_u) \quad \text{for } S_n > \sigma_{ys} \quad (4)$$

where K_F and m are the two material fracture parameters. The stress S_u (ultimate value of elastic net-section stress) was computed from the load required to produce a fully plastic region or hinge on the net section based on the ultimate tensile strength, σ_u .

FIGURE 5 Fatigue crack-growth-rate data for various R ratios on 9310 steel C(T) specimens.

FIGURE 6 Elastic stress-intensity factors at failure and TPFC analyses.

For middle-crack tension, M(T) specimens, S_u is equal to σ_u . For a pure notch-bend specimen, S_u is $1.5 \sigma_u$. For the compact specimen, S_u is a function of load eccentricity and is $1.62 \sigma_u$ for $c/w = 0.5$ (see Ref. 24). The fracture parameters, K_F and m , are assumed to be constant in the same sense as the ultimate tensile strength; that is, the parameters may vary with material thickness, state of stress, temperature, and rate of loading. If m is equal to zero in Eqns. 2 and 3, then K_F is equal to the elastic stress-intensity factor at failure, and the equation represents behaviour of low-toughness (brittle) materials. If m is equal to unity, the equation represents fracture behaviour of high-toughness materials (plane-stress fracture).

In 1973, a relationship between K_F/E and m [23] was found for a large number of materials and crack configurations. Herein, the relationship was used to help select an m value. Because the 9310 steel exhibited a high toughness, an m -value of 0.7 was selected. The corresponding K_F value was $1,150 \text{ MPa}\cdot\sqrt{\text{m}}$ to fit the 9310 steel fracture data. Solid and dashed curves in Figure 6 were calculated from the TPFC for the $w = 76.2$ and 50.8 mm wide compact specimens, respectively. These calculations show how the initial crack length and specimen width affects the elastic fracture toughness.

CRACK-CLOSURE MEASUREMENTS AND CALCULATIONS

The BFS gauge method was also used to automatically measure crack-opening loads from remote load-strain records during the tests. From the FTA Crack Monitoring System [28], compliance offset values (see ASTM E-647) are normally measured and recorded to estimate the crack-opening load as a function of crack length. In the past, a zero percent offset value (OP0), similar to Elber’s

crack-opening load, was extrapolated using the one-percent (OP1) and two-percent (OP2) offset compliance values [29].

For the 9310 steel, the remote BFS method was unable to detect both OP1 and OP2 compliance off-set values at any stress ratio, so a crack-closure analysis using OP0 values could not be performed. However, for the CPCA and CPLR tests at the $R = 0.1$, some OP1 values were measured. These values are shown in Figure 7. Here P_{o1}/P_{max} values are plotted against crack length. The solid symbols show the CPCA test that had a long delay after compression pre-cracking before the CA test was conducted, whereas the open symbols show the results from the CPCA test with no delay after compression pre-cracking. For both tests, the final c/w value was greater than 0.7, but no OP1 values were recorded. These results help explain the large rate differences shown in Figure 5(d). The test with no delay after compression pre-cracking (open symbols) showed nearly constant values and did not show a large rise in the crack-opening-load ratio.

The horizontal dashed line in Figure 7 shows the calculated crack-opening-load ratio from the FASTRAN code [30] for a constraint factor of 2.5. Note that the P_{o1} values are less than the Elber’s crack-opening load. Improved methods need to be developed to measure the proper crack-opening loads, such as that proposed by Elber.

FIGURE 7 – Crack-opening load measurements for $R = 0.1$ tests on 9310 steel.

EFFECTIVE STRESS-INTENSITY FACTOR ANALYSES AND DATA CORRELATIONS

For most damage-tolerance and durability analyses, linear-elastic fatigue-crack-growth analyses have been found to be adequate. Thus, the effective stress-intensity factor [4] is

$$\Delta K_{eff} = (S_{max} - S_o) \sqrt{(\pi c) F} \tag{5}$$

where S_{max} is the maximum applied stress, S_o is the crack-opening stress and F is the boundary-correction factor. Boundary-correction factors account for the configuration (boundaries, holes, crack shape) and type of loading on stress-intensity factors. Herein, the stress-intensity factor

equations in ASTM E-647 [9] were used for C(T) specimens and $S = P/(Bw)$. In general, for any crack configuration, the effective stress-intensity factor range [4, 5] is given by

$$\Delta K_{eff} = U \Delta K = [(1 - S_o / S_{max}) / (1 - R)] \Delta K \quad (6)$$

A crack-closure analysis was performed on the thin 9310 steel using the FASTRAN [30] crack-closure model. In Figure 8, the ΔK_{eff} -rate data correlated well and collapsed onto nearly a unique curve in the low- and mid-rate regimes using the modified strip-yield model in the code. However, the CPLR tests conducted on specimens at $R = 0.1$ to 0.7 fell together but differed from the CPLR tests conducted at $R = 0.9$ and 0.95 . Yamada and Newman [18, 19] have shown elevated closure levels when using both ASTM LR and CPLR testing on two materials. The lower vertical dashed line at $(\Delta K_{eff})_{th}$ is the estimated effective threshold predicted from a large amount of test data on aluminum alloys, titanium alloys and steels based on a normalisation with the modulus of elasticity [27]. The estimated effective threshold agreed well with the rate data measured from the $R \geq 0.9$ tests.

A constraint factor of $\alpha = 2.5$ (plane strain) worked well in correlating the test data over a very wide range in R in the threshold and mid-rate regimes, except for the CPLR tests. But in the high-rate regime, a constraint-loss regime (CLR) was used with a constraint factor of 1.15 (plane stress). The upper vertical dashed line at $(\Delta K_{eff})_T$ is the predicted flat-to-slant (plane-strain to plane-stress behaviour) location [8]. However, the selection of the constraint-loss regime in terms of rates is still a trial-and-error procedure using crack-growth behaviour under variable-amplitude loading [31]. For each R , the high-rate regime is controlled by the fracture toughness and does not correlate in terms of ΔK_{eff} . For example, ΔK at fracture is $K_{Ie} (1 - R)$, where K_{Ie} is the elastic fracture toughness.

The solid lines with circular symbols show the selected ΔK_{eff} -rate baseline curve to be used in the FASTRAN code with a multi-linear crack-growth-rate equation. These data points and other material properties are given in Table 1.

The crack-growth equation used in FASTRAN is

$$dc / dN = C_{1i} (\Delta K_{eff})^{C_{2i}} [1 - (\Delta K_o / \Delta K_{eff})^p] / [1 - (K_{max} / K_{Ie})^q] \quad (7)$$

where C_{1i} and C_{2i} are the coefficient and power for each linear segment, ΔK_{eff} is the effective stress-intensity factor range, ΔK_o is the effective stress-intensity-factor threshold, K_{max} is the maximum stress-intensity factor, K_{Ie} is the elastic fracture toughness (which is, generally, a function of crack length, specimen width, and specimen type), p and q are constants selected to fit test data in either the threshold or fracture regimes. Equation (3) has three terms: (1) Paris-type multi-linear power relation, (2) threshold term, and (3) fracture term. Whenever the ΔK_{eff} was equal to or less than ΔK_o , then the crack would stop growing; and whenever the applied K_{max} value reached or exceeded K_{Ie} , then the specimen or component would fail. The threshold term was developed many years ago to model the fanning with the stress ratio (R) that was caused by load-shedding tests to generate very low crack-growth rates. Thus, ΔK_o was a function of R . However, using the new near-threshold testing procedures (CPGA and CPLR), fanning of the ΔK -rate data does not generally occur with R . Thus, the threshold term was not needed here and ΔK_o was set to zero ($p = 1$).

Figure 9 shows the original ΔK -rate data at various R on the thin 9310 steel [22] and shows how the crack-growth-rate equation fits the data. The high-R curve fits very well in the near-threshold regime but does not fit the R = 0.1 to 0.7 near-threshold data because of load-history effects due to load reduction. Further study is needed in the threshold regime. The TPFC was used to predict the elastic stress-intensity-factor range at failure, $\Delta K_c = K_{Ie} (1 - R)$, from the solid curve in Figure 6.

FIGURE 8 Effective stress-intensity factor against rate relation for 9310 steel.

TABLE 1 Effective stress-intensity factor against rate for 9310 steel

ΔK_{eff} (MPa-m ^{1/2})	dc/dN (m/cycle)	Crack-growth, fracture and tensile properties	
2.30	1.0e-11	$\Delta K_o = 0$	q = 6
2.45	1.5e-10	$\alpha_1 = 2.5$	1.0e-7 m/cycle
2.80	4.0e-10	$\alpha_2 = 1.15$	1.0e-5 m/cycle
3.50	1.0e-9	$K_F =$	1,150 MPa-m ^{1/2}
4.40	2.0e-9	m =	0.7
9.50	1.0e-8	$\sigma_{ys} =$	980 MPa
20.0	1.0e-7	$\sigma_u =$	1,250 MPa
50.0	8.0e-7	$\sigma_o =$	1,115 MPa
120.0	6.0e-6	E =	208.6 GPa

FIGURE 9 Stress-intensity factor against rate and crack-growth equation for various R values.

SINGLE-SPIKE OVERLOAD TEST AND ANALYSES

The results of a repeated single-spike overload test (open circular symbols) are shown in Figure 10 on a 9310 steel C(T) specimen. The specimen was subjected to $S_{\max} = P_{\max}/(WB) = 10.7$ MPa at $R = 0.1$ loading with a frequency (f) of 18 hz after compression pre-cracking. The crack was initiated at the crack-starter notch and grown to $c = 39$ mm under CA loading. Here, a factor of 2 overload was statically applied and then unloaded to zero load. CA loading was resumed and the crack was grown to 54 mm, where a factor of 2.5 overload was applied.

FASTRAN [30] was used to predict crack growth using the ΔK_{eff} -rate curve (see Fig. 8) and the CLR that had previously been determined [22]. The dashed curve is under CA loading while the solid (blue) curve is under the repeated spike overload test. Here the overloads were applied on the basis of cycles instead of crack length. The model predicted the slight delay from the first overload but was reasonable for the second overload. The dashed curve shows the results of constant constraint ($\alpha = 2.5$), which predicted very little crack-growth delay after the overloads.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Fatigue-crack-growth-rate tests were conducted on compact, C(T), specimens made of 9310 steel ($B = 10.2$ mm). Specimens were tested over a wide range in load ratios ($0.1 \leq R \leq 0.9$) to generate crack-growth-rate data from threshold to near fracture. Several loading sequences were used to generate near threshold data: (1) compression pre-cracking constant amplitude (CPCA), (2) compression pre-cracking load reduction (CPLR), and (3) ASTM Standard E-647 load reduction (LR). Stress-intensity-factor range against rate data for each load ratio compared well with test data from the literature on a thinner material ($B = 6.35$ mm) using same test procedures. Very little

difference was observed between the ASTM LR and CPCA/CPLR test methods, although compression pre-cracking allowed lower initial ΔK_i values to start the load-reduction test.

The back-face strain (BFS) gauge method was used to monitor crack lengths and to measure crack-opening loads from remote load-strain records during all tests. But the remote method was unable to measure any crack-opening loads for moderate to high R conditions ($R \geq 0.4$), but some measurements were made at $R = 0.1$. In addition, a crack-closure analysis was also performed to calculate the effective stress-intensity factor (ΔK_{eff}) against rate data using the FASTRAN model. In the near-threshold regime, a plane-strain constraint factor of $\alpha = 2.5$ was required. The fatigue-crack-growth-rate data correlated well onto a nearly unique curve from threshold to near fracture. And the FASTRAN crack-growth equation fit the various R data well. However, some discrepancies were observed in the threshold regime that was suspected to have been caused by a load-history effect.

FIGURE 10 Measured and predicted crack-length-against-cycles under a single-spike overload.

NOMENCLATURE

B	Thickness, m
c	Crack length, m
dc/dN	Crack growth rate, m/cycle
E	Modulus of elasticity, GPa
K_{cp}	Compressive stress-intensity factor during pre-cracking, $MPa \cdot m^{1/2}$
K_{Ie}	Elastic stress-intensity factor at failure, $MPa \cdot m^{1/2}$
K_{max}	Maximum stress-intensity factor, $MPa \cdot m^{1/2}$
P_{max}	Maximum applied load, kN
P_{min}	Minimum applied load, kN

P_o	Crack-opening load, kN
R	Load (P_{min}/P_{max}) ratio
U	Crack-opening function, $(1 - P_o/P_{max})/(1 - R)$
w	Specimen width, m
h	Height of the crack-starter notch, m
c_n	Notch length, m
ΔK	Stress-intensity factor range, $MPa\cdot m^{1/2}$
ΔK_{eff}	Effective stress-intensity-factor range, $MPa\cdot m^{1/2}$
ΔK_i	Initial stress-intensity-factor range before load reduction, $MPa\cdot m^{1/2}$
ρ_c	Dugdale plastic-zone size under compressive load, m
σ_o	Flow stress (average of yield and ultimate tensile strength), MPa
σ_{ys}	Yield stress (0.2% offset), MPa
σ_u	Ultimate tensile strength, MPa

Acronyms:

BFS	Backface strain gauge
CLR	Constraint-loss regime
CPCA	Compression pre-cracking and constant-amplitude test method
CPLR	Compression pre-cracking and load-reduction test method
C(T)	Compact specimen
DICC	Debris-induced crack closure
FCG	Fatigue-crack growth
OPn	Crack-opening load (P_o/P_{max}) ratio at n% compliance offset
PICC	Plasticity-induced crack closure
RICC	Roughness-induced crack closure

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